

The Role of Memory in Psychotherapeutic Treatment

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Abstract

Much data is now available on the effectiveness of psychotherapies on the stability of the change achieved and on the therapeutic relationship, which, in its various conceptual declinations, constitutes the most incisive predictor of outcome. Moreover, the principle that psychotherapy is more effective when it is more specifically oriented towards the psychopathological factors underlying the symptoms is becoming increasingly clear. Many studies have confirmed that the most effective psychotherapists can create deep alliances with a diverse typology of patients, regardless of the relational skills and attachment patterns the patient possessed at the beginning of therapy. An aspect not always considered is 'memory reconsolidation,' which allows modifying or replacing dysfunctional emotional responses with more functional ones.

Introduction

Scientific studies in psychotherapy refer to experimental research conducted rigorously, even in the absence of evidence of the efficacy of the treatment under examination, while excluding those with a methodology that is not considered suitable. Generally speaking, scientific research is open to intersubjective control, clear definitions of concepts and postulates, readable and repeatable procedures, and an experimental method for validating hypotheses [1].

In empirical studies in psychotherapy, therefore, when we speak of outcome research, we mean research that aims to define the changes achieved through treatment by studying what happens at the end of the treatment compared to the starting point (baseline). The biggest problem lies in what is considered the starting point; one must only change the outcome indicator to get opposite results. One historically used indicator to verify the intervention is the reduction of manifest symptoms. However, this remission is not necessarily the only criterion for psychotherapy's 'good outcome' [2]. To usefully refer to a research protocol and its results, it is necessary to consider which outcomes it intends to pursue and whether these aspects have been

investigated with valid and relevant instruments. However, the emphasis placed on the symptom and its weight in assessing the success of intervention has become increasingly attenuated over time also because of the heated debate on the nature and significance of the symptom in psychopathology: symptoms may indicate the presence of a pathological process but say little about the nature of the problem [3]. The definition of the initial pathological state (clinical problem), therefore, must be somewhat isomorphic and congruent with the definition of the type of intervention applied (treatment) and with the definition of what is expected to be changed at the end of the treatment, concerning the initial problem (outcome), investigating several levels simultaneously: symptom reduction, social adaptability, cognitive functioning, management of contextual influences and the degree of perceived satisfaction [4].

Today, much data is available on the efficacy of psychotherapies and the stability of the change obtained on the therapeutic relationship, which, in its various conceptual declinations, constitutes the most incisive predictor of outcome and the principle that psychotherapy is all the more effective, the more specifically it is oriented towards the

More Information

How to cite this article: Guazzo GM. The Role of Memory in Psychotherapeutic Treatment. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(4):222-9.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(4).29

Keywords:

Memory, Psychotherapy, Memory reconsolidation, Dysfunctional emotional responses.

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psychopathological factors underlying the symptoms appears to be increasingly consolidated [5,6] Therefore, the therapist's years of experience and technical skills (relational, personological, technical, empathic, etc.) are called into play in building the therapeutic alliance [7].

Many studies have confirmed that the most effective psychotherapists are those most able to create deep alliances with a diverse typology of patients, regardless of the relational skills and attachment patterns the patient possessed at the beginning of therapy [2,7] These studies, however, have scarcely addressed the role played by memory in holding dysfunctional emotional learnings in a wide range of pathologies.

Memory: Functional Characteristics

The term 'memory' denotes the capacity to retain a complete and lasting trace of the external stimuli experienced (events, images, sensations, etc.) and their responses and recall them when the original stimulus has ceased. More specifically, from a psychological point of view, three different systems have been identified: *sensory memory* of very short duration and small size, which can be considered as a trace that captures our senses (among the various sensory memories, the visual or iconic, in which the information lasts a few hundredths of a second, and the auditory or echoic, which lasts 3-4 seconds, are the most studied); *short-term memory* (also known as working memory), in which incoming information is retained for only a few seconds, unless it is refreshed and consolidated, before being transferred to long-term memory; *long-term memory*, which is capable, in principle, of retaining the information stored in it for a long period, perhaps for the individual's entire life, unless there is a deterioration of the neurological systems involved [9].

Long-term memory comprises four main subsystems [10,11]: 1) perceptual representation, 2) episodic memory (processing of personal events), 3) semantic memory (processing of facts and general relationships) and 4) implicit memory (involved in learning motor, cognitive and behavioural sequences). The latter type of memory, also called procedural memory, is closely related to implicit learning, a form of learning in which a subject's behaviour is sensitive to one or more aspects of a situation and memorizes them without any intentional exploitation and is aware of the explicit notions related to that situation. Implicit memory underlies many of our routine activities: sequential devices involved in activities that can be described through systems of operational rules and the effects of what is called *priming*, i.e. the facilitation of a performance (perceptual or conceptual) based on previous experience, facilitation that does not require conscious retrieval of that experience.

The neurological substrates of explicit (declarative) and implicit (non-declarative) memory activities differ. Brain imaging and positron emission tomography data [12] suggest that procedural knowledge involves anatomy-physiological structures in the prefrontal area, left perisylvian areas, thalamus, basal ganglia and cerebellum. On the other hand, explicit learning stored in declarative memory depends on structures distributed over both cerebral hemispheres in the medial temporal lobe [13].

Despite its importance and development, we still need to learn more about the functioning of implicit memory because, paradoxically, it has been little studied. Procedural learning capacity is present early in normal development and does not seem to change significantly with increasing age, unlike explicit learning capacity.

The various registers of long-term memory are functionally and neuro-anatomically related, although the exact manner of their relationship is still under debate. [14] predicts a sequential mechanism: the perceptual representation system would be the first to act to identify and recognize the shape and structure of stimuli (objects, faces, words, etc.), then semantic memory, and finally episodic memory (which establishes the spatial and temporal framework of the episode).

Both episodic and semantic memory appear to depend on the integrity of the medial temporal lobes (particularly the hippocampus for episodic memory and the para-hippocampal cortex for semantic memory) and the diencephalon, with the prefrontal areas for episodic memory. The gradual consolidation of a memory trace in the long-term system occurs at the end of a process that changes the connections between and within the neocortical regions involved [9].

Data from animal experiments suggest that memory trace persistence depends on the activation of dopaminergic connections at the level of hippocampal and para-hippocampal structures [15]. In any case, the relationship between memory and perceptual integration still needs to be clarified. On the other hand, episodic memory is continuously but slowly enhanced in children from the first year of life. However, only around the age of 5 can we speak of episodic memory, allowing us to imagine the past as such. The proper functioning of this form of memory depends on the integrity of the medial temporal lobes (particularly the hippocampus) and the diencephalon, with the addition of the prefrontal areas. Again, the gradual consolidation of the trace occurs at the end of a process that modifies the connections between and within dedicated cortical regions.

The key variable in episodic memory is the degree of organization. Other things being equal, the more elaborate the organization, the greater the probability of correct and complete recall. During encoding, the

relevant features of an episode must be related to provide a coherent representation. The consolidation of the trace is promoted by external or internal reactivations that may occur in the subject and alter interneural connections in the cortical regions involved. [16] emphasize the primordial role of the hippocampus. The hippocampal cortex encodes consciously learned information and constitutes an index of the various aspects of the episode that can be stored both within the hippocampus itself and in anatomically neighboring structures. Access to a trace from a retrieval index would depend on the reinstallation, during the retrieval phase (recall, recognition), of the operations that took place during encoding. It is also possible, and this question is still being studied, that different traces, representing aspects of the same objects or events partially overlapping, may be stored in different parts of the median temporal cortex, depending on the degree of perceptual-conceptual analysis of the stimulus at the time of storage and the person's previous contact with the same reality [17].

What then happens to a person who has learned to react emotionally in a dysfunctional way to stressful situations and retains the memory over time?

Scientific research shows that the brain's neuroplastic capacity allows the nervous system to reorganize its structure, function, and connections in response to environmental stimuli. But is this capacity, which allows us to learn from experience, also responsible for the long-term encoding of emotional learnings that cause distress in most mental disorders?

The most recent research on memory [18] has identified a particular type of innate neuroplasticity in the brain, known as 'memory reconsolidation', which allows the modification or replacement of dysfunctional emotional responses with more functional ones.

Memory Reconsolidation

For years, it was thought that it was impossible to modify the traces of dysfunctional emotional learnings, consolidated through responding conditioning, found in implicit memory throughout an individual's life. Acquired emotional responses can certainly be temporarily suppressed in various ways (counterconditioning, exposure procedures, emotional regulation strategies, etc.), but such measures do not extinguish dysfunctional emotional learning, creating another type of learning that competes with the undesired behaviour [19,20]. This suggests that all learning that occurs in the presence of strong emotions is blocked in subcortical implicit memory circuits by synapses [21,22]. Several studies [23-26] have shown that the brain, in its evolutionary process, has equipped itself with a key to those 'blocked' synapses, allowing an understanding of how emotional memory works. The researchers, working with animals, reactivated

emotional learning, finding that its 'blocked' neural state had temporarily changed to 'unlocked', de-consolidated and labile, allowing the learning to be cancelled entirely, along with the behavioural responses, also dysfunctional, that it had activated. However, the 'unblocked' circuit soon reverts to a 'blocked' condition, so researchers have given this type of neuroplasticity called 'memory reconsolidation' [18]. In other words, memory consolidation is a process that can last from a few minutes to a few hours, in which the conversion of a memory trace from an unstable form to a stable form, which can thus be recalled even days later. This later recall is a dynamic process because it returns the consolidated memory to its unstable form, which requires reconsolidation. Still, if some interference intervenes, the memory may be lost forever, leading to a 'reconsolidation block'. This phenomenon is evidenced in the laboratory by a typical response conditioning experiment, in which a mouse is exposed to a neutral (conditioned) stimulus, e.g. a light, combined with a painful (unconditioned) stimulus. After several repetitions of the conditioning, the rodent shows fear, manifesting the characteristic 'freezing in place' whenever the light (conditioned stimulus) is switched on [27].

Memory reconsolidation, therefore, is an innate brain mechanism whereby newly learned experiences directly modify or replace memory contents acquired in previous learning. This updating of memory contents brings about a change both at the subjective level and at the level of neural coding: it is a process of experience-driven neurological change [28].

As can be inferred from research findings, this mechanism can be used in psychotherapy to record dysfunctional emotional learning [29].

Psychotherapy as a Means of Neural Recoding

The efficacy of a treatment cannot be considered the only modality capable of verifying how much the subject's symptomatology and mental functioning change following the treatment (return and/or reduction of symptoms concerning the baseline and maintenance of the same). Still, it is also necessary to refer to a qualitative approach to follow the transformation of the typical variables of a particular pathology (Depression, OCD, etc.) and the peculiarities of that subject and the course of the relationship that this transformation produces and sustains over time. Psychotherapeutic treatment is so complex as to make its evolution unpredictable: slight variations in the initial conditions produce effects, even very significant ones, that are not deterministically linked to the conditions themselves. The essential problem of clinical research, therefore, consists in the need to deal with the complexity of the object of study and its development over time: that is, it must be intervention-focused, it must respond to multiple problems that

cannot be fractioned and attempt, at the same time, to understand the set of behaviours on which it must operate [27].

Psychotherapists aim to help their patients effectively change dysfunctional behaviours, emotions and thoughts, producing profound and lasting changes. However, their accounts of how and why these changes occur differ considerably, as do their methods.

The relevance of the research findings on memory reconsolidation for psychotherapy has, therefore, paved the way for a new common ground between neuroscientists and clinicians in understanding why clinical symptoms of various disorders (depression, OCD, insecure attachment, post-traumatic symptomatology, etc.) are maintained by emotional learnings stored in implicit memory [29]. This approach has been used mainly in cases of depression, comparing brain activity levels in patients before and after therapy using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI). The differences have been observed, identifying localized changes in specific areas: a decrease in the activity of the amygdala, which plays a key role in attributing emotional meanings to memories, and an increase in the activity of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, which is responsible for planning and regulating behaviour [30].

The thus delineated picture of the brain process of unlocking emotional learning, which allows for the unlearning, rewriting and deletion of new learning during the period of lability, is of paramount importance for psychotherapy, as it allows for consciously explicating the stages of consolidation, significantly increasing the effectiveness with which a therapist can dissipate and/or delete a wide range of dysfunctional emotional responses [31,32]. The erasure of emotional learning can be verified by observing the following distinctive indicators of change (not to be confused with counter-active methods that compete with the emotional roots of the person's symptoms but do not eliminate them [33]:

- *Lack of reactivation*: an emotional response can no longer be suddenly and sustainably reactivated by events, situations or triggers that previously activated it;

- *Cessation of symptoms*: the symptoms of behaviour, emotion, somatization or thought that were an expression of that emotional response disappear permanently;

- *Effortless permanence*: the non-reappearance of the emotional response and symptoms continues without any preventive intervention.

However, for reconsolidation to occur, an additional critical experience must occur while the memory is still reactivated; this new experience consists of perceptions that deviate strongly from what the reactivated target memory expects both qualitatively

(the outcome does not occur at all) and quantitatively (the magnitude of the outcome is not fully expected) [34,35]. After reactivation, neural memory circuits remain in a de-consolidated or labile state for about five hours, as can be inferred from several studies [36-39]. During this 'reconsolidation time', the target learning can radically disappear and, consequently, be erased from emotional memory. When deleting a de-consolidated memory, the deletion is limited to exactly the target learning of the reaction without compromising other closely related emotional learnings that have not been directly reactivated [40,41]. In other words, reconsolidation allows new learning to act directly on the target learning, cancelling it out if the new learning contradicts and disconfirms the original learning.

After five hours, labile neural circuits naturally reconsolidate and can no longer be altered by new learning until they are reactivated and new experiences are created.

As we have seen, the process of changing emotional learning, following neural rules to unlearn and delete a target learning, consists of implementing three phases of the transformation sequence [28]:

Phase 1. Reactivation: reactivating target knowledge by presenting salient cues or contexts from the original learning.

Phase 2. Maladaptation/unlocking: with reactivation in place, create an experience that is significantly at odds with the pattern and expectation of functioning of the target learning; this stage unblocks synapses and makes memory circuits refreshable by new learning.

Phase 3. Deletion (or modification by new learning): during the five hours or so before the synapses have relocked, a new learning experience is created that contradicts (deletes) or complements (modifies) the labile knowledge of the target.

These phases, referred to as the 'transformation sequence', can significantly improve psychotherapeutic practice beyond the theoretical reference orientations of individual therapists [27].

In psychotherapy, the execution of each step of the transformation sequence necessarily requires the knowledge and mastery of certain preparatory steps to perform transformation through the access sequence [28]:

Step 1. Accurate knowledge of the specific symptoms to be eliminated. Actively clarify with the patient what to consider as symptoms (dysfunctional behaviours, somatization, emotions and/or thoughts that one wants to eliminate, etc.) and when they occur, i.e. the situations and contexts that evoke them (an interview that can help to define the symptoms, situations and contexts that can evoke them can be found in Tab. 1). This information is necessary to undertake Step 2 effectively.

Table 1: Semi-Structured Interview to Identify Symptoms and the Environments and Situations that Evoke Them

INTERVIEW				
Subject:		Age:	Interviewer:	Date:
Symptom(s):				
Instructions: interview the person presenting the symptom and answer the questions by placing an X on 'Y' for YES or 'N' for NO in the corresponding boxes in the 'A' (Answers) column. For each 'YES' answer write a qualifying comment in the line below the question or on a separate sheet of paper.				
Questions			A	
MEDICAL FACTORS	1. Did the symptom appear during a particular season?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	2. Did the symptom occur during a physical discomfort? (Headache, Pain, Heartburn, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	3. Did the symptom appear in a deprived condition? (Thirst, Hunger, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	4. Did the symptom appear after taking a drug?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	5. Can the symptom be associated with an emotional condition? (Agitation, Anxiety, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS	6. Does the symptom occur if he sleeps little or badly? (Pavor, sleeping a few hours or too many, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	7. Does the symptom manifest itself more during food or diet-related routines?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	8. Does the symptom, under certain circumstances, always occur?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, when?</i>			
	9. Does the symptom, under certain circumstances, never occur?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, when?</i>			
	10. Is the symptom felt more at certain times of the day?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, when?</i>			
SITUATIONAL FACTORS	11. Does the symptom occur more in the presence of certain people?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, with whom?</i>			
	12. Is the symptom felt more in times of boredom?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which ones?</i>			
	13. Is the symptom present in relation to certain activities?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which ones?</i>			
	14. Does the symptom appear in response to aversive stimuli (noise, discomfort, etc.) or frustrations?	S	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
	15. Does the perception of the symptom vary depending on the context or situation? (Work, peer group, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which one?</i>			
SITUATIONAL FACTORS	16. Is the symptom an opportunity to complain to someone? (Attention-seeking, Consideration, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, with whom?</i>			
	17. Does the symptom provide an opportunity for social isolation? (Poor stimulus environment, etc.).	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, when?</i>			
	18. Is the symptom present with other behaviours or is it part of a symptomatic chain?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, which ones?</i>			
	19. Is the symptom experienced as the expiation of a guilt towards oneself or others?	Y	N	
	<i>If YES, to whom?</i>			
20. Is the symptom perceived more intensely if the subject is alone?	Y	N		

<i>If YES, on what occasions?</i>		
21. Is the symptom more pronounced if the subject experiences anxiety, fear or panic? (Motor agitation, etc.).	Y	N
<i>If YES, under what circumstances?</i>		

Step 2. Recovery of the target learning. Retrieving in explicit memory the details of the emotional learning or pattern that underlies and drives the presenting symptom. Knowledge of this material, in turn, allows the therapist to perform Step 3.

Step 3. Identifying experiences that are at odds with emotional learning. Identify a vivid experience (past or present) incompatible with the emotional target's reality model recovered in Step 2, such that both cannot be true.

Mastery of these three Steps indicates that the transformation sequence can begin, taking into account that the retrieval of the emotional learning in Step 2 constitutes the major part of the therapeutic work, which continues with Step 3, in which the therapist has the task of finding an incompatible vivid experience to be used both in Step 2 of the transformation sequence and for the new learning in Step 3.

With the implementation of the whole sequence described (Steps 1, 2, 3) and the Verification step (Observations of 'Non-Emotional Reactivation', 'Symptom Cessation' and 'Effortless Maintenance'), the whole process of applying memory reconsolidation is put into practice by determining the unlocking of neural circuits of a target emotional learning, revisiting, rewriting and updating old circuits.

Examples of applications of the memory consolidation process, with different symptoms and psychotherapy approaches, can be found in [27].

Conclusions

The emotional brain uses learning in implicit memory to instantly anticipate and recognize, as self-defense, similar dysfunctional experiences that might occur in the future. This, however, causes the worst emotional experiences of the past to persist as vivid emotional realities even in the present, conditioning people's lives (e.g. fears, attachment styles, etc.), with the fear that the unwanted response could reoccur at any time. The discovery of memory consolidation made it possible to understand that dysfunctional emotional responses that originate in the limbic system can be regulated with a psychotherapeutic pathway through the creation of learnings and preferential responses in prefrontal regions that send regulatory neural connections to subcortical regions [42]. The new learnings create new neural circuits, erase existing and unwanted learning, and allow the person in therapy to recover their emotional learnings through adaptive experiential awareness, ensuring well-being.

Based on these findings, memory reconsolidation can be considered a general model of change for use in clinical practice and to integrate various psychotherapeutic orientations.

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